

Pest incidence in Central Luzon, the rice granary of the Philippines

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A team from the Entomology Department of IRRI investigated the incidence of rice pests in farmers' fields at more than 100 sites in five provinces of Central Luzon: Bulacan, Pampanga, Nueva Ecija, Tarlac, and Pangasinan. About 95% of the area surveyed was planted to improved varieties. About 25% of the planting were the improved short varieties IR26, IR30, IR32, IR36, and IR38 which have insect and disease resistance and high yield potential. About 70% were the short or tall varieties and lines IR5, IR8, IR20, IR22, IR747, IR1529, IR1561, C4-63G, C4-137, and C22 which have high yield potential but are susceptible to insects or to diseases, or to both. The remaining 5% were local varieties Burma, BE3, Kennedy, Milagrosa, Tjeremas, glutinous rice, and others.

In several barrios of Candaba, Pampanga, both local and improved varieties (including IR26) and lines, except IR32, IR36, and IR38, were infested with the brown planthopper *Nilaparvata lugens*, the rice leaf folder *Cnaphalocrosis medinalis*, the white-backed planthopper *Sogatella furcifera*, and the green leafhopper *Nephotettix virescens*. From a distance, the slightly pale, yellow color of the rice plants could be mistaken for nitrogen deficiency. Close examination showed brown planthoppers at 1,000 nymphs/hill. In the adjacent rice fields the curled-up, whitish leaves of the rice plants were more visible. The farmers thought that planthoppers were causing the damage; the damage was in fact caused by the rice leaf folder.

In Bulacan and Nueva Ecija where larger tracts of rice land were surveyed, the plants were severely infected by tungro virus, and infested with more than 100 green leafhoppers/hill. Such pest populations, even without tungro, could cause severe stunting and yellowing. Fields planted to IR32, IR36, and IR38 showed strong resistance to

tungro and its vector. Stem borer damage was not significant.

In Tarlac and Pangasinan, insect infestation was very low; tungro was randomly distributed. The limited insect

damage was related to the low insect pest incidence rather than to the use of resistant varieties since most farmers in that area still plant traditional varieties.

GENETIC EVALUATION AND UTILIZATION

Drought tolerance

Screening for seedling drought response

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Because undependable or erratic onset of monsoon rains is common in many regions where rainfed rice is grown, seedling-stage drought is a major obstacle to crop establishment.

Breeders recognize the problem, but little organized screening of rices for reaction to seedling-stage drought has been done. Earlier, we developed a greenhouse technique to screen rices for drought tolerance at various growth stages using a natural-drying-of-soil concept. It gave reproducible results using the variety Moroberekkan as a susceptible check variety, and IR1529-430-3 as a tolerant check. In the IRRI phytotron, we screened 206 rices from rainfed upland, lowland, and deep-water regions (deep-water rice is

A test in the IRRI phytotron demonstrates varietal differences found in the percent of survival (%S) of eight cultivars subjected to seedling drought. (The IR20 rows are guard rows.)

Seedling survival of rices from varying hydrological and cultural origins after exposure to severe growth chamber drought.

Variety/line	Origin ^b	Survival rate (%) after exposure ^a for			
		7 days	10 days	12 days	15 days
Rikuto Norin 21	Japan (U)	0	0	—	—
Kinandang Patong	Philippines (U)	3	3	—	—
30-E	Liberia (U)	3	0	—	—
63-83	Ivory Coast (U)	65	5	—	—
Monura	Bangladesh (DW)	85	37	—	—
Rangi Kharna	Bangladesh (DW)	95	90	5	0
Sigadis (check)	Indonesia (RL)	98	83	26	0
Khao Dawk Mali 4:2-105	Thailand (RL)	100	75	30	0
Goirol	Bangladesh (DW)	100	100	60	5

^aRices with survival rate less than that of the check (Sigadis) at 10 days were not tested at 12 and 15 days.

^bU = upland; DW = deep water; RL = rainfed lowland.